

OUT THERE, IN HERE:

PRESERVATION STRATEGIES FOR MULTIMODAL CULTURAL HERITAGE IN 3D AND XR

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Abstract – This paper presents *Out There*, a multimodal, interdisciplinary project that captures 2D photography, 3D models, Gaussian splats, volumetric video, and oral histories to document the work of a legally blind sculptor in a remote outdoor setting. Designed to serve both as a digital preservation strategy and a collaborative framework, the project examines challenges such as file format volatility, interoperability, metadata standards, and storage demands. Drawing on evolving best practices and preservation models, we propose strategies for maintaining long-term access to complex digital assets while centering collaboration with artists and domain experts. This work-in-progress highlights both the potential and the limitations of current 3D/XR preservation efforts and contributes a replicable model for cultural heritage practitioners working with similarly layered digital projects.

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cultural heritage, these digital products are not only tools for engagement and interaction but records of what we choose to preserve and how we represent and interpret the original objects. Driven by accessibility, sustainability, and collaboration, a new Virginia Tech University Library (VTUL) initiative aims to digitize the *Out There* sculpture trail in Virginia as a multimodal, interdisciplinary project that integrates 2D, 3D, virtual reality (VR,) augmented reality (AR), and oral history technologies and experts to create a virtual experience of the exhibit. This paper introduces the project and examines the preservation complexities and strategies for stewarding these diverse media types over time. Centered on file formats, metadata practices, storage, and documentation, it proposes a reproducible preservation model designed to support modular, scalable, and meaningful long-term access to complex digital cultural heritage objects.

I. INTRODUCTION

As 3D and extended reality technologies become increasingly embedded across a wide range of sectors from entertainment and education to architecture, medicine, and cultural heritage, the need to consider how to preserve the outputs of these technologies becomes increasingly urgent. Particularly regarding tangible and intangible

II. THE PROJECT: *OUT THERE* SCULPTURE TRAIL

Charlie Brouwer¹ is an American artist known for his wooden sculptures and mixed media drawings and paintings that reflect the daily experiences with place, community, and nature. A full-time artist by 2008, in 2022, Charlie was diagnosed with a vision disability that has left him legally blind with his remaining sight gradually deteriorating. His most

¹ Charlie Brouwer: <https://www.charliebrouwer.com/>

impactful pieces are wooden sculptures, a material that degrades over time and requires the artist to manually restore pieces as needed. A prominent permanent exhibit is a sculpture trail titled *Out There* composed of 38 sculptures located on his remote, wooded property in southwest Virginia.

Mr. Brouwer's vision, the relative inaccessibility of the sculpture trail, and the physical deterioration of the wood present challenges that impact community engagement with a celebrated Virginia artist and add to the urgency to preserve. VTUL is partnering with Mr. Brouwer to use a combination of photogrammetry, extended reality capture, 2D photography, and oral to fully assemble this sculpture trail as a multimodal version of the experience.

Planned in three primary phases, VTUL is currently in Phase 1 to 3D scan the 38 sculptures using photogrammetry and 2D scanning a collection of mixed media flat file drawings that complement many sculpture exhibitions. During Phase 2, our Applied Research in Immersive Experiences and Simulations (ARIES) team will join us to assist in capturing the environment of the sculpture trail, including the geography and soundscapes, using Gaussian splatting. Phase 3 will incorporate oral history methods to capture Mr. Brouwer's narration of the stories of the sculptures through audio recording and volumetric capture.

III. ENVIRONMENTAL SCAN

In education, 3D models and extended reality are increasingly used as pedagogical tools in the classroom. For example, [1] presented a case study on the use of 3D printing in an elementary biology class, emphasizing the accessibility benefits for blind students. Photogrammetry and 3D printing in archaeology have similarly enhanced the teaching of cultural heritage [2]. A study comparing dynamic and static visualizations found that interactive 3D models had a positive impact on students in science fields [3]. The Virginia-Maryland College of Veterinary Medicine's AR Anatomy programs² have been successfully integrated into the curriculum, offering a step between classroom instruction and interaction with a live animal with AR animal models.

Tangible and intangible cultural heritage have benefited from advances in 3D and extended reality capture. For example, the Magazzini del Sale historical landmark in Venice was captured using photogrammetry to document its full architectural complexity, allowing for a holistic narrative of its structure and significance [4]. In Slovenia, a photogrammetry project focusing on outdoor wooden sculptures highlighted the dual purpose of preserving vulnerable artworks while enabling reinterpretation and enhanced public interaction through AR/VR [5]. Even underwater cultural heritage is being made accessible through adapted photogrammetry techniques [6]. Recent efforts to analyze emerging practices in documenting intangible cultural heritage—such as song, dance, and storytelling—have found that 3D modeling, motion capture, and AR/VR are the most widely adopted tools for capturing and representing ephemeral practices [7].

Other projects are designed to virtually reconstruct entire structures based on photogrammetric capture and through multidisciplinary collaboration. The virtual reconstruction of the Bridge of Avignon, a remote historic site in France, used photogrammetric capture combined with expert input from multiple disciplines [8]. Similarly, the development of a virtual museum to represent Eastern Mediterranean artifacts illustrates the potential for digital curation to honor cultural significance while enabling multimodal engagement [9].

Photogrammetry, while rooted in early photographic practices, remains a dominant method for capturing highly detailed and photorealistic 3D models [10]. It relies on capturing hundreds of overlapping images to generate accurate spatial and textural data. However, its reliance on controlled lighting presents challenges, particularly when working with reflective surfaces. Cross-polarization techniques have become standard for minimizing specular reflection in object photography [11]. An emerging development in this space is Gaussian splatting, which diverges from traditional mesh-based modeling. Rather than producing surfaces defined by vertices and polygons, splatting techniques use point clouds composed of "splats"—data-rich points that carry information on position,

² VMCMV's Augmented Reality Anatomy: <https://guides.lib.vt.edu/vetmed/vranatomy>

color, size, and orientation [12]. This method offers improved rendering of reflective surfaces and more efficient capture of complex visual characteristics, as seen in new projects like [13].

Many recent efforts have been made to guide preserving 3D data, such as the primer in the DPC Technology Watch report [14], results from DANS “Shaping the 3D World” workshop on developing 3D preservation roadmaps [15], and adapting metadata models to better represent 3D [16]. The most comprehensive guide the authors found for the specific preservation of 3D data in cultural heritage offers practical guidance on each component of the data curation lifecycle [17]. Much of the focus is solely on 3D data rather than AR/VR preservation and doesn’t yet include the newer techniques like Gaussian splatting, but do offer critical frameworks for managing metadata, access and reusability, and acceptable file formats.

IV. METHODOLOGY

VTUL’s 3D program launched in 2019 with the support of a Council on Library and Information Resources Digitizing Hidden Special Collections and Archives grant (697) to digitize 300 insects using photogrammetry and helped establish the library’s initial workflows for 3D digitization and preservation. This multi-modal project to capture *Out There* expands these workflows by integrating additional capture techniques including Gaussian splatting, volumetric capture, and audiovisual and photographic documentation. Preservation strategies for this project prioritize long-term sustainability, open file formats, storage scalability, and future usability.

VTUL’s preservation strategies for digitally preserving and storing 3D models prioritize the ability to reconstruct the object accurately in the future [18]. For preservation, we use the eXtensible 3D (X3D)³ file format, a non-proprietary ISO standard with embedded metadata. For access and visualization, we adopted the Graphics Library Transmission Format Binary (GLB), a lighter, open format optimized from its original Global Library Transmission Format (glTF) package for efficient rendering and minimal storage requirements [19].

The integration of Gaussian splatting introduces additional preservation challenges. As a much newer technology anticipated to eventually challenge photogrammetry, Gaussian splatting might be produced as a Polygon (PLY) format, or in its newly created SPlat Zip (SPZ) format, a lighter, royalty-free, open-source format developed by Niantic Labs. Their blog [20] posits that SPZ is approximately 90% smaller than PLY. SPZ may be considered for access purposes but carries higher preservation risk due to its low adoption and limited development.

Volumetric capture generates larger and more complex datasets and though it has a wide range of possible formats, there is no consensus around a preservation format. Output formats are based on the capture method and intended use. End-user access might be a more standard MP4 containing the audio, video, and mesh, however, there is higher adoption of proprietary formats like 4DS and Alembic (ABC). Hybrid exports using OBJ + PNG, glTF, PLY, and GLB are also possible and more sustainable but may require additional metadata.

Table 1. outlines file formats under consideration for each content type, considering: open-source status; adoption by users; file size range based on local examples and estimations; and estimated preservation risk from low to high based on accepted guidance like the most current Library of Congress Recommended Formats Statement [21]. This project also includes 2D images and audio/video components but are not included in the table.

TABLE I. File Formats Under Consideration

	File Format	Open	Adoption	File Size Range	Preservation risk
3D Models	X3D	Yes	High	10-700 MB	Medium
	glTF/GLB	Yes	High	10-35 MB	Medium
	PLY	Yes	High	10-250 MB	Medium
Gaussian splats	PLY	Yes	High	200-500 MB	Medium
	SPZ	Yes	Medium	10-50 MB	High
Volum. capture	OBJ+ PNG	Yes	Low	500 MB -2 GB	Low
	ABC	No	Low	1-5 MB	High
	4DS	No	Low	2-10 MB	High

	<i>File Format</i>	<i>Open</i>	<i>Adoption</i>	<i>File Size Range</i>	<i>Preservation risk</i>
	MP4	No	High	5-50 MB	Medium

V. RESULTS & DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

Collaboration and Interdisciplinary Design —

One of the primary risks to digital preservation in projects like this lies in unstructured collaboration across units—particularly when preservation is not integrated early in the creative and technical workflow. For *Out There*, collaboration spans library departments (3D lab, ARIES, Publishing and oral history, metadata) and external partners (the artist and subject matter experts). To avoid bottlenecks and data loss, early alignment on formats, responsibilities, naming conventions, and access strategies have been prioritized. Establishing clear expectations around deliverables and preservation needs—such as retaining raw and intermediate files—helps prevent accidental omissions. We also aim to support the artist's creative goals while ensuring the digital assets remain stable, portable, and accessible in the long term.

File Formats — As shown in Table 2, for 3D models, we will continue to use X3D as the preservation format. X3D is a non-proprietary ISO standard with an active development community, support for embedded metadata, and strong interoperability with other tools. Its structure supports packaging multiple files—including TIFFs, point clouds, meshes, textures, and lighting meshes—alongside technical and descriptive metadata. This approach avoids lock-in to proprietary formats while still allowing access to derivatives and conversion as needed. Initially, X3D was also used for access, but rendering and latency issues led to the adoption of GLB for public-facing use. GLB is lightweight, non-proprietary, machine-readable, and easily integrated into web platforms, making it a better access solution moving forward.

Gaussian splats are still new enough that no established format exists for preservation. We will keep more than may be necessary, including the original PLY and JSON for preservation. PLY formats can be optimized by reducing vertices in the

structure of the model. These will also be packaged with technical and descriptive metadata, the point cloud, and texture files.

Volumetric capture introduces additional complexity, as proprietary formats such as ABC and 4DS are commonly embedded in the production pipeline. While we cannot avoid these formats entirely, we will attempt to extract and preserve more stable alternatives, such as OBJ + PNG sequences for mesh and texture, and MP4 for access. All variants—proprietary and open—will be retained until long-term preservation guidance becomes clearer for volumetric content.

TABLE II. Preferred File Formats

	<i>Preservation</i>	<i>Access</i>
3D models	X3D	glTF
Gaussian splats	PLY, JSON	PLY (lower vertices)
Volumetric capture	OBJ + PNG	MP4

Preservation Strategy — Since launching 3D and Digital Humanities initiatives, VTUL adopted the strategy of preservation through reconstruction for complex and multimodal digital objects. Each component of the project is preserved independently as a discrete asset and connected through metadata. Each item will have unique technical metadata, READMEs, and the necessary components to reconstruct the data in the future—such as TIFFs, mesh, and texture for a 3D model. The *Out There* project applies this modular model, emphasizing sustainability, transparency, and reusability across its diverse digital assets. Storage considerations will be monitored for each file type, however, size is also impacted—the complexity of the texture file for a given model. For 3D models, we follow a modified version of the Smithsonian 3D Metadata Model⁴ that incorporates DublinCore and the DLP's built-in PREMIS-based audit and fixity service.

VI. CURRENT PROGRESS & NEXT STEPS

We are currently in Phase 1 of this project. To date, we have scanned five exhibits worth of mixed media drawings as part of the 2D component, and five of the sculptures on the *Out There* sculpture trail

⁴ VTUL 3D Metadata Model:
<https://doi.org/10.7294/21230690.v2>

are in the process of being digitized through photogrammetric methods. We are also collaborating closely with the artist to collect descriptive metadata for both 2D and 3D components. This work will culminate in a proof-of-concept package on the Virginia Tech Digital Library's pre-production server in the summer of 2025. Planning for Phase 2 is underway and includes expanding the Virginia Tech Digital Library Platform (DLP) built on Amazon Web Services to support growing demands on both the front-end for interactive access and rendering, and the back-end to accommodate storage and migration. Phase 2 planning also includes coordinating with the 3D lab, ARIES, and Mr. Brouwer to begin the environment capture with Gaussian splatting.

As the project develops, we will continue to monitor emerging technologies, such as recent work in 4D Gaussian splatting and hybrid point cloud approaches [22] and better prepare for migration and adaptations for file formats. Anticipating proprietary format challenges, especially for volumetric capture where vendor-locked workflows are common, will ensure we can respond to interoperability challenges. Finally, we will address file size and storage implications for Gaussian splats and volumetric capture outputs to optimize storage.

VII. CONCLUSION

This project aims to develop a reproducible, preservation-focused model for multimodal digital heritage that accommodates 3D modeling and emerging technologies like Gaussian splatting and volumetric capture. By foregrounding file format sustainability, modular metadata, and open documentation, the workflow supports both long-term stewardship and meaningful user access. Our approach emphasizes interdisciplinary collaboration with artists and technologists to ensure cultural and creative intent is not lost in translation. As a work in progress, this project will evolve alongside technologies, emphasizing the need for scalable, iterative preservation strategies in an increasingly complex digital landscape.

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